
Worktime Scheduling with Genetic Algorithms, Neural Networks and Constraint Programming.

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Abstract: The work presents an automatic work scheduling system based mostly on genetic algorithms, along with an analysis of various possible solutions. We discuss possible methods of encoding the work schedule in the chromosome, possible crossover and mutation operators, and possible forms of fitness functions. The possibility of combining genetic algorithms with local search methods and constraint programming is also analyzed.

1. Introduction

Optimizing employee work schedules in a plant is a common problem faced by all companies. Properly matching the number of people with specific skills to each working hour translates into significant productivity improvements. Another important element in such a scenario is properly adjusting each employee's workdays to their wishes. Flexible scheduling is one of the most important factors influencing employee satisfaction. Another problem is when an employee scheduled to work on a machine, for example, becomes ill that day or the machine breaks down. Such incidents cause a significant drop in plant productivity. In such situations, it is crucial to recreate the schedule to minimize machine downtime or employee absence. Creating a schedule from scratch is a very difficult and complex task, especially when considering employee wishes.

Manually creating work schedules is time-consuming, expensive, often suboptimal, and prone to human error. This leads to employee dissatisfaction, low-efficiency schedule creation, and financial penalties resulting from human error under the Labor Code. Automating this process should solve these problems and, in addition, increase staff satisfaction with the created schedules by fulfilling more employee requests, ensuring more optimal staffing, and eliminating the occasional feeling of injustice among staff that other employees have been assigned a better schedule.

Because creating an optimal work schedule (one that meets all the necessary requirements and a maximum of the optional wishes of employees and managers) is an NP-complete problem, where the number of possible schedules, even in a medium-sized company, is so large that it is impossible for a computer program to evaluate all solutions and select the best one, much less is it possible for a human to create such a schedule.

Full automation based on artificial intelligence methods can provide a solution to this problem. However, this is not a simple matter due to the extremely complex dependencies present in work schedules. In this paper, we focus on adapting genetic algorithms [1] to work scheduling [2,3]. Two main problems are that work scheduling is a three-dimensional problem (these dimensions are: employee, position, and time), whereas existing optimization methods are designed for two-dimensional problems, and the presence of numerous constraints and interactions in such a system.

Additionally, we analyze the use of local search implemented in the crossover operator in the genetic algorithm and constraint programming.

In our research, we conducted:

- Analysis of various methods for representing the problem on a chromosome, along with the resulting possibilities and limitations, including the suitability and adaptability of crossover operators, mutation operators, and crossover conflict resolution operators, the number of parents in crossover operators, and the frequency of local searches,
- Selection of fitness functions,
- Design of local search operators,
- Comparison with attempts to solve the problem using constraint programming.
- Analysis of additional issues relevant to this problem.

Experience from our previous work on optimization algorithms in production and trade [4,5], as well as studies available online, indicate that in this type of combinatorial problem, solutions found by algorithms using artificial intelligence methods are characterized by an average 10-15% improvement (reduction in time, distance, or other optimized quantity) compared to solutions manually generated by humans. In the case of work scheduling, the possible improvement can be expressed by various criterion functions and may vary depending on the criterion function adopted. Calculating this improvement in percentage terms requires a comparative analysis of many real-world scheduling cases in various companies. We are currently collecting and analyzing these cases. F. M. Howard [6] reports that after implementing scheduling automation in one hospital, conflicts among staff were more than doubled and employee satisfaction increased by an average of 0.8 points on a 5-point Likert scale compared to manually generated schedules.

It is also possible to use constraint programming elements, which we analyzed in this paper using the OR Tools solver developed by Google [18]. Recently, attempts to use various neural network structures as an auxiliary mechanism in work scheduling have also appeared in the literature [8-10]. However, at this stage, we have too little data collected to attempt to use such solutions.

2. Genetic Algorithms

In this section, we present the solutions we analyzed based on genetic algorithms and their combination with local search. In the final part of the chapter (Section 2.8), we will also discuss the use of constraint programming.

In the genetic algorithm [1], we first encode the solution to the problem in a chromosome (section 2.1). We then randomly create a population of N individuals (e.g., $N = 100$). From this point on, we iteratively perform the following operations:

- determining the fitness function of all individuals (section 2.3)
- selecting individuals as parents (section 2.6)
- crossover (section 2.4) with an optional local search (section 2.8)
- elimination (section 2.7) This process continues until we determine that a suitable solution has been found, or a predetermined number of iterations have elapsed, at which point we select the best existing solution.

Genetic algorithms are an excellent method for finding the optimal solution to very large and complex problems. For example, if a problem is encoded in 100 binary positions (zeros and ones), the number of possible solutions is $2^{100} \approx 1030$, and that's how many solutions would need to be tested to find the best one (a so-called brute force method). Genetic algorithms, on the other hand, thanks to their intelligent search process, are able to find the best solution by searching through just a few thousand different solutions, often finding a solution in seconds or minutes (depending on the complexity of the objective function), whereas brute force would take many trillions of years and would be practically infeasible.

The advantage of genetic algorithms over local search methods (which in rare cases can be reduced to gradient methods) is that in practical, complex problems, the objective function has many (dozens, even hundreds) arguments and is extremely complex, full of local minima. Local search methods get stuck at these local minima, unable to approach any global minimum (because in complex problems there are often more than one equivalent global minima). Genetic algorithms, on the other hand, are quite good at finding one of the global minima or approaching it so closely that in practical applications, it makes no difference. However, once the optimization process approaches the global minimum, local search methods can sometimes be used in the final phase to accelerate finding the final solution.

Work scheduling (regardless of the method) should be carried out in the smallest, independent units of the company, because it is easier to find an optimal solution, provided that employees working in different departments of the company do not have the opportunity to replace each other in given positions.

2.4. Wvertime Schedule Coding in a Chromosome

Considering that each workstation must have an assigned employee, a chromosome for a single shift could be defined as a one-dimensional array whose index corresponds to the workstation and whose value contains the assigned employee. However, if the algorithm's goal is to create an optimal work schedule spanning multiple shifts and multiple days (which is always the case in practice), the problem can be encoded in the chromosome in several other ways. One is to use a two-dimensional array, with the workday as an additional dimension, as shown in Fig. 1. In multi-shift work, the day is replaced by a shift in the above representation. In practice, it is often the case that a given employee can only work at a single workstation (although several employees can simultaneously share the same workstation, e.g., in a store, restaurant, etc.), which slightly changes the encoding method.

In addition to the scheme shown in Fig. 1, other ways of encoding the problem are also possible. For example, if we are creating a weekly (7-day) work schedule and have 20 employees, 3 shifts each day (0 - day off, 1 - first shift, 2 - second, 3 - third), this can be encoded in a chromosome of length $7 \cdot 20 = 140$, where each position will represent the shift of a given employee on a given day (0 to 4) [2,11,12]. This encoding produces a one-dimensional chromosome, but the dependencies between its positions remain (e.g., on a given day, 5 employees are required for a given shift). As a result, the complexity of the problem does not decrease, but schedule compliance is checked in a different way.

	Stanowisko 1	Stanowisko 2	Stanowisko 3	Stanowisko 4	Stanowisko 5
Dzień 1	Pracownik 4	Pracownik 2	Pracownik 5	Pracownik 4	Pracownik 1
Dzień 2	Pracownik 2	Pracownik 3	Pracownik 1	Pracownik 4	Pracownik 5
Dzień 3	Pracownik 5	Pracownik 3	Pracownik 2	Pracownik 1	Pracownik 4

Fig. 1. Example chromosome representation for 3 days with 5 employees and 5 positions.

2.1. Constraints

In the problem of work scheduling, there are a number of requirements, which we will also call constraints. These can be divided into mandatory (hard) and optional (soft) constraints. Mandatory constraints must be met for the schedule to be valid and acceptable. Optional constraints do not have to be, but the more of them that are met, the better the schedule should be considered. Therefore, we strive to satisfy as many optional constraints as possible.

Mandatory requirements are conditions that must be met for a schedule to be considered valid:

- The employee can only be assigned to a position they are capable of performing.
- The employee must work in a manner consistent with the labor code, e.g., they cannot work two shifts in a row.
- The required number of employees must be assigned to the positions required to be filled.

In this work, we adopted the following optional requirements:

- The employee is assigned to their preferred machine.
- The employee works on their preferred days.
- The employee works their preferred number of days.

Given the defined hard and soft requirements, we proposed several crossover operators discussed in Section 2.5.

2.2. Fitness function

The fitness function determines the value of each individual (i.e., each solution constituting a potential schedule) in the population. For the traveling salesman problem, this would be the distance it must travel to visit all the cities on the list. However, for some problems, the fitness function may be difficult or even impossible to define using a simple formula. This most often applies to cases where simulations must be conducted, the output of which is the value of the fitness function. The fitness function can be maximized or minimized during the optimization process.

We analyzed three approaches to constructing a fitness function for work scheduling:

1. The fitness function contains only soft requirements, i.e., employee wishes and other possible parameters that are better met, but not required. Hard requirements that must be met, such as the number of employees on a given shift (sometimes a specific number, sometimes a range from 0 to 0), or assumptions arising from the labor code regarding when, how much, and at what intervals an employee can work, are controlled first during population initialization and then in the crossover operator, which prevents the creation of individuals that do not meet these parameters.
2. The fitness function contains both hard and soft requirements. An example of such a fitness function is the sum of the number of employees in their preferred positions (of course, within the range of positions they can work in), the number of employees working on their selected days, and the difference between the number of days selected by the employee and the actual number of days worked. This fitness function is maximized in the optimization process. The fitness function incorporates both hard (with higher weights) and soft (with lower weights) requirements. In this case, there is no control in the crossover operator, and individuals are allowed to temporarily arise that may not meet the required assumptions (required number of employees, labor code), and the fitness function's task is to gradually eliminate them during optimization.
3. Combine both approaches by using approach 2 in the initial optimization phase to ensure adequate population diversity, and then switching to approach 1 to avoid creating invalid individuals in the final phase. Ensuring population diversity is discussed later in this article.

2.3. Crossover Operators

The purpose of the crossover operator is to combine information from two or more different chromosomes (parents) into a single chromosome (child), which may represent a better solution than its parents.

The way the problem is encoded in the chromosome determines the type of crossover operators we can use. With the coding method shown in Figure 1, it's impossible to directly use the simplest crossover operator, which involves

randomly selecting two parents and a random split point, and then the first child (the first offspring) receiving the first part from the first parent and the second part from the second parent, while the second child receives the reverse. This will very often lead to the situations shown in Figure 2. However, with longer chromosomes, abnormal children will be generated much more often than normal ones.

We used several crossover operators:

- A splitting operator based on work days
- A splitting operator based on occupied positions
- A splitting operator based on occupied positions that repairs the incorrect chromosome
- A splitting operator based alternately on work days and occupied positions
- The AEX operator
- Operators from the HGreX series

Figure 2 shows a crossover operator based on a half-split based on workdays. This crossover operator improves the matching of specific workdays selected by employees and the number of workdays. To improve the distribution of preferred positions, an operator based on occupied positions should be used. The best matching is achieved by alternating between day-based and position-based operators. Due to the large number of chromosome errors that arise with this approach, it is necessary to add a repair function for such chromosomes by finding free employees and inserting them in place of the faulty gene. This repair can be performed in various ways. In some crossover operators, it is an integral part of the repair function.

Fig. 2. Chromosome crossover operation resulting in one normal offspring and one abnormal offspring

Various crossover operators have been developed that implement a mechanism for correcting faulty genes (also called collision avoidance) [13,14]. One of the most popular is the AEX (alternating edges crossover) operator. This operator selects one element from the first parent and then, from the second parent, the element following the element most recently selected from the first parent. This operation is performed alternately between the two parents until a complete descendant is generated or a collision occurs. A collision occurs when, according to this procedure, an element that already exists in the descendant is selected. In such a case, instead of the selected element, the descendant is assigned a randomly selected element from among the elements not yet present. Then, the basic procedure continues. Figure 3 shows the AEX operator's operations.

Fig. 3. Example of AEX operator operation (the figure does not take into account the possible occurrence of collisions)

The H...X series of operators, which are extensions of the AEX operator, are particularly interesting, as they incorporate local search elements [15-17]. However, their use requires defining the concept of adjacency as the cost of traversing two elements. This cost is very well defined, for example, in the Traveling Salesmen Problem, where it is simply the distance between the cities represented by the elements. Instead of selecting elements from parents alternately, the HRndX operator randomly decides which parent the next element will be selected from. The HProX operator, in turn, selects the parent with greater probability for a lower traversal cost between an element from a given parent and the last element added to the child. There is also a fully deterministic operator, HGreX. This operator will always select the parent in which the cost of traversing the last element of the child is lower. If a conflict occurs (the selected element that we want to add already exists in the descendant), we should insert a random element instead, which is not yet present in the new chromosome (exactly the same as in the AEX operator).

A significant problem in work scheduling is defining the transition cost. Therefore, our idea was to replace the choice that minimizes the transition cost with a locally more optimal solution. For example, if on a given employee's workday, the possible position from one parent represents the first shift and from the other, the second shift, we choose with greater probability the position that aligns with the employee's preferences regarding the shift they would like to work that day.

It is not advisable to use only local search based on domain knowledge to create an optimal schedule for a large organization, because this method would likely only find a local minimum, worse than what a genetic algorithm can find. Local search alone has very limited potential for exploring the solution space [7].

Another important issue here is the optimal balance of local and global search. Too much local search is not recommended, as it does not lead to good results, but a small share can help find a better solution. We analyzed this issue in detail in our previous paper, "Local Search in Selected Crossover Operators"[4], with respect to optimizing the distribution of goods in a warehouse and the traveling salesman problem. In that paper, we also analyzed the use of local search in other crossover operators, such as AEX and KPoint. These operators do not inherently contain a local search component, but it can be used in various scenarios, for example, as a way to resolve conflicts when constructing offspring from parents. We are currently analyzing the possibility of using the results described there in scheduling work.

It is also worth mentioning that more than two parents can be used to create offspring. Increasing this number improves the algorithm's convergence speed for most crossover operators, particularly the operator shown in Figure 2. This problem is beyond the scope of this article. Interested parties are referred to our publication "Optimization of Warehouse Operations with Genetic Algorithms" [5].

2.4. Mutation Operators

The goal of mutation is to perform a change within a single chromosome. It is used to avoid a situation where no chromosome in the population contains genes at the selected positions that lead to the best solution to the problem, and where these genes cannot be obtained in crossover operations.

Mutation is typically implemented as a random change at random locations on random chromosomes. First, x random chromosomes are selected, regardless of their fitness function values, and then a random operation is performed on their genes. The mutation operator must be adapted to the chromosomal representation of the problem.

In the case of independent gene representation (where changing one gene does not force the change of another gene), the most commonly used mutation operators are gene swapping or bit flipping. Figure 6 shows a mutation operator using bit flipping.

However, an operator based on the random swap of two genes in a chromosome iterates through the entire population and performs a mutation according to a defined probability. Unfortunately, because such an operation can cause chromosome damage, before making a permanent change to a chromosome, it is necessary to check whether it will still be correct after the change.

Fig. 4. Mutation by bit flipping

Several special mutation operators have been developed for dependent gene representation. Based on tests, one of the best is RSM (Reverse Sequence Mutation). This operator randomly selects two points on the chromosome and then reverses the order of the elements contained in the positions between these two points.

The probabilities of mutation are generally low because its side effect is the disruption of the order that the crossover operation is trying to create, which is something we are trying to avoid (this does not apply to certain specific versions of genetic algorithms, which we do not use here).

2.5. Selection Operators

The goal of the selection operator is to select individuals that will then be used during the crossover operator to generate offspring. This selection can be deterministic, partially random with a preference for better individuals (tournament selection, roulette selection, and their variants), or fully random.

Deterministic selection. This method involves selecting a certain number of individuals with the best fitness function score. Because it is a completely deterministic solution, this method is characterized by rapid convergence but poor solution exploration. This means that in the initial epochs, we obtain a rapid increase in the quality of individuals, but the solution can get stuck (and in larger problems almost always will) in a local minimum. This occurs due to the premature elimination of individuals with a poorer fitness function value (depending on whether we are minimizing or maximizing the fitness function, this may be higher or lower), whose chromosome fragments may contain good partial solutions that are not present in the better individuals.

Fig. 5. Distribution of selection probability during selection. The label contains the value of the individual.

Roulette Selection. In roulette selection, we throw a virtual ball onto a virtual disc containing each individual's identifier. We select the individual whose field it lands on. The field corresponding to each individual occupies a larger portion of the wheel the higher the fitness function (assuming maximization of the fitness function), which increases the probability of selecting better individuals. In the basic variant of roulette selection, the relationship between the fitness function value of a given individual and the field assigned to it is linear. However, this relationship can be expressed as any monotonic function, depending on how much (or how little) we want to reward better individuals. Although tournament and roulette selection operate on different principles, from a practical perspective, they are almost equivalent with the appropriate selection of the number of candidates in tournament selection and the form of the function mapping an individual's fitness to its field on the roulette wheel. A graphical representation of roulette selection is provided in Fig. 5.

Tournament Selection. Tournament selection involves first drawing a number of candidates from the entire population, separately for each parent, and then selecting the one with the best fitness function. If the number of candidates equals the number of individuals in the population, this is equivalent to deterministic selection. As the number of candidates decreases, weaker individuals have an increasing chance of becoming parents. The optimal number is often a few candidates (4-8). With two candidates, selection is weaker, while with a single candidate, it is equivalent to completely random selection.

2.6. Elimination Operators

These operators eliminate individuals that do not advance to the next epoch. They can therefore also be considered selection operators for individuals advancing to the next epoch. Three basic solutions are used here:

1. Only children advance to the next epoch (in which case, there must be as many of them as the population size).
2. We sort the children and parents together, and from this total, as many individuals as the population size advance to the next epoch.
3. Only a few of the best parents advance to the next epoch, and we supplement the rest with children (known as elitism).

It is important that the selection pressure, or the strength with which we favor better individuals, is considered jointly for the parent selection operator and the operator for eliminating individuals that do not advance to the next epoch. This strength should be optimal. Too weak a strength unnecessarily prolongs the process. Too strong a strength may result in the optimal solution not being found due to depletion of the population's genetic material. Furthermore, a variable selection strength can be used, increasing with optimization. This is because with progressive optimization the differences between individuals decrease and it is then worth promoting the best individuals more strongly.

2.7. Local Search

Domain knowledge within local search can be incorporated into the genetic algorithm's operation in various ways, with the first choice being its implementation in the crossover operator. The simplest example of domain knowledge in this

case is that if a given employee wants to have a specific amount of free time, the search process should be directed to allow them to do so (without considering the rest of the schedule at this point).

It is not possible to use domain knowledge-based local search alone to create an optimal schedule, because this would only lead to a local minimum, which is worse than what the genetic algorithm can find. Local search alone has very limited potential for exploring the solution space.

In the final stage, we attempted to use the n-opt algorithm (specifically, 2-opt) to improve the resulting solution. However, it was not used in the final solution because the need to take into account constraints (e.g. an employee must have a certain break between two shifts and others) with each change made by n-opt made the process very complicated.

3. Constraint Programming

Constraint programming is a method for solving combinatorial problems that aims to find feasible solutions from a very large set of candidates, where the problem can be described by arbitrary constraints. It often employs backtracking and constraint propagation techniques. Constraint programming refers to the development of a plan, in this case a work schedule (rather than programming in a computer language). It is based on feasibility (finding a feasible solution) and focuses on constraints and variables, not the objective function. This is a significant difference between constraint programming and genetic algorithms. An example of a problem that lends itself to constraint programming is employee scheduling.

It's worth comparing constraint programming with genetic algorithms. The advantage of genetic algorithms is their extensive ability to explore the solution space; they can explore a large solution space and find good solutions even for complex problems. Another advantage is flexibility: they can utilize various objective functions and constraints. A disadvantage of these algorithms is the time required to find a solution. They may require many generations (iterations) to converge on an optimal or satisfactory solution, and the optimization process typically slows down as it approaches the minimum.

The advantages of constraint programming include the ability to find optimal solutions to well-defined problems, making it suitable for situations where precision is essential. Another advantage is that this method handles complex constraints and interdependencies between variables well. It is effective for small and medium-sized problems.

The disadvantages of constraint programming include scalability issues: that is, as the dimensionality and complexity of the problem increase, efficiency decreases. This was clearly demonstrated by our tests with the OR Tools package for creating work schedules. Creating a schedule for large organizations took so long that we didn't see it finished, and as a result, this method proved impractical for these problems. Another disadvantage is that writing a program implementing constraint programming from scratch is more complex than writing a corresponding program implementing genetic algorithms.

Considering the advantages and disadvantages of both methods, it is worth trying to combine them. Although this is not a simple approach to the problem of work time scheduling, it will be an element of our future work. However, such attempts have already been described in the literature [11,12].

3.4.1. OR Tools

Google OR Tools [18] is a library implementing constraint programming. OR Tools provides an interface in the most popular programming languages, including C#.

To develop a model that schedules work hours according to assumptions and constraints, we analyzed the possibilities of using the Google OR Tools library. The entire process begins with creating a CpModel object and entering all the assumptions and constraints prepared in the previous steps.

```
var model = new CpModel();
var work = new BoolVar[constraints.EmployeeCount,
                    constraints.DataRanges.Shifts.Count,
                    constraints.DataRanged.Days.Count];
```

The first constraints defined are the assignment of a maximum of one shift each day.

```
foreach (var shift in constraints.DataDanged.Shifts)
{
    work[employee.Value, shift.Value, day.Value] = Model.NewBoolVar($"work{employee.Value}
                                                                    _{shift.Value}_{day.Vaule}");
    temp[shift.Value] = work[employee.Value, shift.Value, day.Value];
}
AddContsraint(model, assumptions, "One shift per day", LinearExpr.Sum(temp) == 1);
```

To add a constraint, we use the `AddConstraint` auxiliary function, which adds it both to the model and to an auxiliary variable used to later identify specific constraints if a solution to the problem is not found. The next step is to add all the schedules already added by the user for a given period. We have provided only sample code snippets to illustrate its style. Those interested can find more details in the OR Tools documentation [18].

Next, we create a linear function object for the optional constraints and then add them to it, starting with the employee preferences and their requests. We then specify constraints on the number of consecutive changes. Finally, all constraint functions are minimized, and a solver is created, responsible for solving the given problem, taking into account its call parameters. The parameters can define, among other things, how long the function has to find a solution, whether to search for the first solution that meets the conditions, or the most optimal solution.

4. Neural Networks

We considered two types of neural network implantations. Both use Q-learning, but they are differently applied to our problem.

The chosen algorithm must be able to learn to generate a correct and optimal schedule without a large dataset. This limitation significantly limits the choice of machine learning algorithms. Considering that reinforcement learning is capable of learning without a supervising trainer and can do so on relatively small datasets, we consider the choice of this algorithm a good decision. The biggest challenge in designing a program that generates schedules using reinforcement learning is appropriately representing the problem. Representing the constraints as probabilities proved to be a challenge that can be solved by adding a layer to the algorithm that appropriately encodes the data.

Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement learning is method in which an agent learns optimal action strategies by performing actions in an environment where decisions are evaluated based on the rewards and penalties it receives. During an iterative process, the agent adapts its policy accordingly, based on which it makes decisions, striving to maximize the reward function. After training, the agent is able to quickly and optimally perform operations based on its policy. In the case of a scheduling problem, the agent's actions include assigning a given employee to a specific day and machine. The environment in which the agent will operate is the full work schedule.

Q-Learning

The most popular implementation of reinforcement learning is an algorithm using a value matrix Q . The Q matrix contains information about the value of the reward function for each pair of actions and the current state of the environment. In each learning iteration, the values in the Q matrix are updated using the Bellman equation (Pavlevski, 2021) presented the following Bellman Equation:

$$Q(s, a) = r(s, a) + \gamma \max_a Q(s', a)$$

- r – reward function
- s – state of the environment
- a – action to be performed on the environment
- γ – discount factor

The γ factor determines how much previous values of Q influence future decisions. For a value of 0, all previous decisions are ignored, while for a value of 1, even the oldest values influence the new value of Q . Selecting the appropriate value of this coefficient is crucial for the optimal operation of the algorithm, because the performed action does not always have to immediately bring a positive result, but it is important to explore the given action (Sutton and Barto, 2018)

Deep Q-Learning

While a standard reinforcement learning algorithm handles problems with a narrow and limited solution space well, it encounters difficulties in complex problems (Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning, 2015). Since generating work schedules in a plant is a complex problem and the number of possible actions an agent can take increases significantly with larger data sets, it is possible that some current state-action pairs will not be tested, meaning that the value of Q will not be known for such a case. A solution to this problem is to replace the Q matrix with a neural network that will approximate the value of Q for each action in a given state. This solution adds complexity to our algorithm, but allows us to analyze cases for which the model has not been trained.

In the case of scheduling, the input to the neural network will be:

- The current schedule in encoded form
- Machine requirements (employee qualifications for each machine)
- Employee preferences regarding the number of workdays
- Employee preferences regarding machines in the form of a bit mask
- Employee preferences regarding specific days in the form of a bit mask

The output is an approximate value of Q for each possible action the agent can perform. A simplified diagram of the neural network is shown in figure below. By using a neural network to approximate the value of Q , one can create a model that can generate schedules even for plants whose data it was not trained on. Such generation would not be possible with a standard matrix Q , because representing the state as a key would always equal an undefined value of Q for the unknown plant. In the case of deep reinforcement learning, the neural network can approximate such a value without significant problems.

Implementation of Genetic Algorithms – based Sheduling

We have experimentally evaluated the methods on sample sets of data. The data includes the company requirements about the number of employees on each shift and the employees' preferences. To make the comparison possible we established the same criterion (fitness function) for each method.

$$F = \text{Sum}(\text{Pref}) + c * \text{Sum}(\text{Req})$$

where

F is the fitness function – the lower the better.

Pref expresses the employees' preferences and Req the company requirements. For each unsatisfied preference we add 1 to Pref and for each unsatisfied requirement we add 1 to Req.

c is a coefficient which expresses the importance of requirements in relation to the importance of preferences. In the experiments we set $c=10$.

The presented below code fragments do not contain the whole source code of particular methods, but only the main parts, which are required to explain how the methods work.

5. Experimental Evaluation

The source code, datasets and obtained results (schedules and optimization progress) can be found in the attachments.

The input data in the attached files is in the following format:

```
3 2,3 1 3 3 1 2 1,2 2
1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1
1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1
1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1
1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0
```

Each column represents one shift. The first row shows the organization requirements about the number of employees at each shift. If there are two numbers separated by a comma, the first one is the minimum, the second one – the maximum number of employees on that shift. The remaining rows contain the employees' preferences. „1“ at a given shift means „I do not have anything against working at that shift“. „0“ means „I don't want to work at this shift“.

6. Conclusions

Scheduling work is a very complex issue due to the high complexity of the problem, numerous constraints, and strong interconnections between individual variables. However, automating this process offers numerous benefits. These algorithms can quickly analyze numerous assumptions and parameters and, based on them, create a work schedule. This frees up a significant portion of valuable work time for those who previously performed this manually, and they can now focus on other key aspects of their work, increasing the efficiency of the entire company. The system creates

work schedules by striving to meet both the needs of the organization and its employees to the greatest extent possible, according to the weights assigned to each need. The system described here requires further development to implement both more complex conditions and to accelerate and improve its performance. One of the future development directions is the combination of genetic algorithms, local search, and constraint programming, as described in the previous sections.

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